

A STUDY ON JOB SATISFACTION AMONG THE WORKERS OF MRF LTD, WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO KOTTAYAM UNIT

Dr. S. Selvendran

Associate Professor of Commerce, Angappa College of Arts and Science,
Coimbatore, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: Dr. S. Selvendran, “A Study on Job Satisfaction among the Workers of MRF Ltd, With Special Reference to Kottayam Unit”, International Journal of Applied and Advanced Scientific Research, Volume 3, Issue 1, Page Number 109-113, 2018.

Introduction:

A major part of man’s life is spent in work, is a social reality and social reality and social expectation to which man seems to conform. It is always of greater interest to know why man work and at which level and how he/she is satisfied with the job. The success or failure of an enterprise depends mostly on how best the employee working there are satisfied.

Statement of the Problems:

This study is an attempt to analysis and investigates the job satisfaction of employees in an organization. Satisfaction of employees about this job is different from person to person.

Objectives:

- ✓ To analysis the opinion of employee working in MRF LTD.
- ✓ To make a study about welfare measure provided by the company
- ✓ To study about safety measures provided by the company
- ✓ To make a study about employee feel about management policies and procedure.
- ✓ To make a study about the facilities provided by the company.

Scope of the Study:

- ✓ The scope of the study includes evaluation of job satisfaction among non managerial employees.
- ✓ It is highly useful to company in case of promotion and facing incentives.
- ✓ It plays a vital role in selection of right employees to the job.
- ✓ Helps to maintain better quality of work life of employees.

Hypothesis of the Study:

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference between level of retirement benefit provided by the company and management policies and procedures of the organization.

Alternative Hypothesis: There is a significant difference between level of retirement benefit provided by the company and management policies and procedures of the organization.

Limitations of the Study:

- ✓ The work in the MRF is peace rate system workers are not ready to waste time of interview.
- ✓ Since job satisfaction is a mental attitude it can’t be measured accurately
- ✓ Limited availability of time is another major limitation of the study
- ✓ The result derived from the study is not applicable to other organisations

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1: Classification on the Basis of their age

Age	Sample Size	%
18 - 28	48	32.00
29 – 38	42	28.00
39 – 48	36	24.00
49 – 58	24	16.00
Total	150	100.00

Source: Primary Data

Classification on the Basis of Their Age:

Inference:

Table 1 shows that classification on the basis of their age. Here 32% belong to the age group 18 -28, 28% belongs to the age group 29 – 38, 24% belong to the age group 39 -48 and 16% belong to the age group 49 – 58.

Opinion about Career Growth Opportunities:

Opinion	Sample Size	%
Highly Satisfied	36	24
Satisfied	96	64
Highly Dissatisfied	0	0
Dissatisfied	18	12
Total	150	100

Source: Primary Data

Opinion about Career Growth Opportunities:

Inference:

From the above table we can see that 64% of the employees are satisfied with career growth opportunities and 24% are highly satisfied but 12% are dissatisfied.

Opinion about Relationship between Colleagues:

Opinion	Sample Size	%
Yes	138	92
No	12	8
Total	150	100

Inference:

From the above table we can see that 92% of the workers have good relations with their colleagues but 8% have no relations.

Opinion about Safety Measures:

Opinion	Sample Size	%
Excellent	9	6
Good	54	36
Average	72	48
Poor	15	10
Total	150	100

Inference:

From the above table we can see that 48% of the workers have average opinion about safety measures and 36% have good opinion.

Opinion about Welfare Measures:

Opinion	Sample Size	%
Excellent	18	12
Good	78	52
Average	54	36
Poor	0	0
Total	150	100

Inference:

From the table we find that 52% of workers are good opinion about welfare measures and 36% of workers have average opinion and only 12% have excellent opinion.

Opinion about Facilities Provided by the Company:

Opinion	Sample Size	%
Highly Satisfied	38	25
Satisfied	84	50
Highly Dissatisfied	10	7
Dissatisfied	18	12
Total	150	100

Inference:

From the above table we can see that 56% of workers are satisfied with the facilities provided by the company. 32% are highly satisfied and 12% have dissatisfied

Chi-Square Analysis:

Null Hypothesis H₀: There is no significant difference between level of retirement benefit provided by the company and management policies and procedures of the organization.

Alternative Hypothesis H₁: There is a significant difference between level of retirement benefits provided by the company and management policies and procedures of the organization.

Level of significance -5% = .05

Degree of freedom

$(R-1)(C-1) = (4-1)(4-1) = 9$

Table value = 16.9

Calculated value = 53.84

Inference:

According to chi square analysis, in this case table value (16.9) is less than calculated value (53.84).ie, $16.9 < 53.84$.so the null hypothesis is rejected.

Null Hypothesis H₀: There is no significant difference between safety measures and welfare measures provided by the company.

Alternative hypothesis H₁: There is a significant difference between safety measures and welfare measures provided by the company.

Level of significance -5% = .05

Degree of freedom

$(R-1)(C-1) = (4-1)(4-1) = 9$

Table value = 16.9

Calculated value = 63.14

Inference: According to chi-square analysis, in this case table value (16.9) is less than calculated value (63.14). I.e. $16.9 < 63.14$. Hence null hypothesis is reject

Findings:

- ✓ Most of the employees are married
- ✓ Majority of the workers are working in engineering department
- ✓ More than half of the employee's qualification is SSLC.
- ✓ Majority of the workers have 6-10 years of experience
- ✓ Majority of them have salary of 5001-8000
- ✓ Most of them are satisfied with their work
- ✓ Majority of them are satisfied with the training programme conducted in the company
- ✓ Majority of the workers are satisfied in the working conditions.
- ✓ Most of them are satisfied in the career growth opportunities.
- ✓ Majority of the employees have good opinion about the relationship between colleagues.
- ✓ There is only average opinion about the safety measures provided by the company.
- ✓ Most of them have good opinion about the welfare measures.
- ✓ Most of them are satisfied with the facilities.
- ✓ Majority of them have good opinion about the management policies and procedures.
- ✓ Most of them have average opinion about the entertainment benefit.

Recommendations:

- ✓ Provide transport facilities for those workers who are living away from the company
- ✓ The management should reduce the heavy work load given for each employee and this increase the rate of job satisfaction.
- ✓ Deserving workers should be duly recognized by way of suitable rewards, prizes for good work.
- ✓ Provide more comfortable rest rooms for employees working in night shifts.
- ✓ Improve the first aid facility by providing more medicines.

Conclusion:

MRF Ltd. Is having a very food corporate image among the type manufactures catering to the needs of commercial vehicles passenger cars two wheeler and three wheeler in two radial and cross play segment The workers in MRF Ltd felt that they appointed in suitable post compared with their capability of qualification. The interpersonal relationship between the workers is satisfactory. The job environment of the workers considering the working conditions, timing and frequency of night shifts, safety measure etc are good enough. But the conveyance facility provided by the company is not satisfactory. The company us providing all the welfare measures as statutory required. The training and development programmes and the disciplinary procedures adopted by the company are good enough. The workers felt that they enjoyed a good social status by working and associating with MRF unit of Kottayam.

References:

1. Gupta C.V, Human Resource Management, Sultan Chand and Sons, New Delhi.
2. Kothari C.R., Research Methodology, K. K. Gupta for New Age International Pvt. Ltd, New Delhi.
3. Sashi K. Gupta and Rosy Joshi, Human Resource Management, Kalyani Publishers, New Delhi,
4. Bockerman, Petri; Ilmakunnas, Pekka,” Interaction of working conditions, job satisfaction, and sickness absences: Evidence from a representative sample of employees”, Social Science & Medicine, Aug2007, Vol. 67 Issue 4, p520-528
5. K. Veerakumar (2016) article titled “A Study on Impact of Customer Satisfaction on Brand Loyalty” International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education, Vol-I, Issue-I, June – 2016. P.No.661-663.